

MAJOR AND MINOR TIMBERS OF KENYA AND THEIR COMMERCIAL USES

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ABSTRACT

The global timber trade has for years been too familiar with an assortment of available African timbers, reputed for their appearance in terms of colour, grain, pattern and durability. African forests are fast disappearing through over-exploitation as a result of demand for agricultural land. Kenya, the home of some of these valuable hardwoods, has been similarly affected, with its forest land cover declining from high 28% to a low 1.7% within the last 5 decades. Today Kenyan forests consist mainly of exotic fast-growing species (Eucalypts, Cypress and Pines), that supply the local demand for industrial timbers (utility poles, posts, construction timbers, pulp and paper, veneer and board materials). The furniture industry now relies on hardwoods imported from Central and Western Africa, Tanzania, Mozambique, Zimbabwe and S. Africa. The wood carving industry, with some 30,000 wood carvers engaged in the industry, still depends on hardwood species available locally. Being still a heavy consumer of fuelwood and charcoal, with indigenous hardwood species being preferred, it is to be expected that indigenous hardwood forests in Kenya will decline further, with fewer of what used to be an extensive list of indigenous species that provided the source of commercial timbers of the country. The list of exotic and indigenous species presented in this paper, not exhaustive by any means, comprises mainly the common commercial species, with brief notes on appearance, properties, availability and uses. There is a number of the lesser known species, about which little or no information is available, mainly used for artisanal work, fuelwood and charcoal.

KEYWORDS: Timbers-Africa-Kenya-Forests-Industrial Timbers-Softwoods-Hardwoods-Furniture-Wood Carving-Species-Exotics-Indigenous-Appearance-Properties-Uses.

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the Forest cover of Kenya has declined to low of 1.7 % of the land area, from a relatively high 28% in the early 1960s. . The Kenyan Forest Department established that in 1999 had a stocked area of approximately 78,000 ha, of which the exotics consisted of 48.8% cypress, 34.7% pines, 8.3% Eucalyptus spp., and only 8.2% of unmanaged or badly managed indigenous forests.

Therefore the exotic softwood plantations form the bulk of Kenya's industrial wood raw material, distributed as follows:

Pulp and Paper – Cypress and Pines;

Poles and Posts – Eucalypts. Wattle

Boards and wood-based Panel products: Cypress, Pine, Eucalypts, with a smaller volume of local and imported hardwoods.

Structural and Construction timbers: Eucalypts, Cypress, Pines.

Interior Joinery (doors, window frames, paneling etc.): Cypress, local and imported hardwoods.

Interior furniture: Cypress, Pine, local and imported hardwoods

Exterior joinery, furniture, cladding, decking etc.: Pine Cypress, Eucalypts, local and imported hardwoods.

Woodcarving: Local hardwoods (*The country has some 30,000 wood carvers*).

In November 1999, all allocation, harvesting and exploitation of indigenous forests (now conservation forests) were suspended in Kenya. In March 2000, there was a Presidential ban on timber harvesting in all government plantation forests, except for a few logging companies which had concessions at the time of the ban being allowed to log. Although the ban persisted up to 2012, it made little difference. And now, it is almost business as usual.

The Kenyan Timber Industry today heavily depends on importations, especially hardwoods, from Central and Western Africa, Tanzania, Mozambique, Zimbabwe and S. Africa.

It is also to be noted that Kenya is a heavy consumer of fuelwood and charcoal (black gold). Most hardwoods, and especially indigenous hardwoods are preferred, hence the drain on indigenous timber species, and severity of deforestation.

The list of indigenous species comprises mainly the common commercial species. There is a number of the lesser known species about which little or no information is available, mainly used for artisanal work, fuelwood and charcoal.

EXOTIC HARDWOOD AND SOFTWOOD PLANTATION SPECIES

Eucalyptus saligna. Eucalyptus, Sydney blue gum, or simply blue gum

The colour of the heartwood ranges from almost white to pink or dark red. The grain is straight or interlocked, texture medium to coarse, fairly hard, coarse, even textured and reasonably easy to work. Density: 850 kg/m³

Uses: Mainly telegraph/transmission poles, fencing posts and agricultural poles, and also for general building construction, panelling, boat-building, flooring, furniture, cart wheels, boxes, crates, handles, ladders, agricultural implements, railway sleepers, hardboard, particle board (MDF) and wood-wool.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Eucalyptus regnans. Australian Mountain Ash

The heartwood is pale red when freshly cut, turning orange-red or red-brown with age; it is clearly demarcated from the pale brown sapwood. The grain is interlocked, texture coarse. Quartersawn surfaces sometimes have a ribbon figure of light and dark stripes.

The wood is fairly heavy, with a density of 720 to 920 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, poles, stakes, fencing posts, outdoor furniture, wheels, decking, shingles, flooring, railway sleepers, agricultural implements, joinery, turnery, musical instruments, food containers, wood wool, cooperage, pallets and boxes.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Eucalyptus camaldulensis. River red gum, Murray red gum, red gum. Mkaratusi (Swahili- Sw)

The heartwood has a red colour, turning red-brown upon exposure, and is clearly demarcated from the paler sapwood. The grain is interlocked, straight or wavy; often producing an attractive figure, texture is moderately coarse. The wood is moderately heavy, with a density of 680 to 980 kg/m³

Uses: Mainly used as poles, posts, construction, railway sleepers, packing cases, fibreboard and particle board.

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Eucalyptus robusta. Swamp mahogany. Mkaratusi (Sw)

The heartwood is pale red when freshly cut, turning orange-red or red-brown with age; it is clearly demarcated from the up to 5 cm wide, pale brown sapwood. The grain is interlocked, texture coarse. The wood is fairly heavy, with a density of 720 to 920 kg/m³

Uses: Poles, posts, construction, outdoor furniture, cart wheels, pallets, boxes, flooring, railway sleepers, agricultural implements and food containers,

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Eucalyptus grandis. Flooded gum, Rose gum.

The colour of the heartwood ranges from almost white to pink or dark red, the sapwood paler. The grain is straight or interlocked, texture medium to coarse with a density of 540 to 775 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, flooring, joinery, panelling, shingles, boat building, cart wheels, poles, posts, outdoor furniture, boxes, crates, handles, ladders, agricultural implements, railway sleepers, hardboard, particle board and wood-wool.

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Acacia mearnsii. Black wattle, Wattle.

The sapwood is straw colored with a reddish brown to dark brown heartwood and bands of gold to dark brown. Basic density: 510 kg/m³

Uses: The main use of plantation forests of wattle in Kenya has been for tanning extraction, but that stopped in the late 1990s, and land under wattle plantations put to other uses.

Other uses include poles, fencing posts, tool handles, woodfuel and charcoal production.

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Acacia melanoxylon. Australian blackwood.

The heartwood is golden brown to dark brown or almost black, often with a reddish tinge and dark streaks, distinctly demarcated from the white to straw-coloured sapwood. The grain is usually straight, sometimes interlocked or wavy, giving a fiddle-back figure; the texture is fine to moderately fine. The wood surface is highly lustrous, with a density of 515 to 710 kg/m³

Uses: High-quality furniture, cabinet making veneer construction, tool handles, musical instruments, bentwork, turnery and fence posts.

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Bischofia javanica. Bishopwood

The heartwood is purplish brown to reddish brown, darkening upon exposure, sharply demarcated from the narrow, pale brown to pale reddish brown sapwood. The grain is generally interlocked, texture moderately fine to rather coarse and even. The wood surface is rather dull to slightly glossy. Bishopwood is medium-weight to moderately heavy and moderately hard to hard. The density is 670 to 845 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, beams, posts, docks, bridges and decking, flooring, joinery, interior finish railway sleepers, furniture, lining, agricultural implements, carving, billiard cue butts. for pulp and paper production, for the production of veneer and plywood.

Grevillea robusta. Silky oak, Southern silky oak, Australian silver oak, Beef wood

Heartwood is a light to medium reddish brown with grey to light brown rays. The wood exhibits the strongest figure in quartersawn pieces, similar to Sycamore, and has a density of 590 kg/m³

Uses: Furniture, cabinet-making, joinery, paneling, boxes, toys, construction work, window joinery, fencing poles.

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Tamarindus indica. Tamarind, Madeira mahogany. Mkwaju (Sw)

Heartwood is a deep reddish to dark brown, sometimes with a purplish hue, heartwood portions tending to be narrow and usually only present in older and larger trees. The pale yellow sapwood is very wide and sharply demarcated from the heartwood. Density 850 kg/m³

Uses: Furniture, pestles, mortars, carts and boat building, panelling, wheels, axles, gears for mills, ploughs, planking for sides of boats, wells, mallets, knife and tool handles, mortars and pestles

Acrocarpus fraxinifolius. Pink cedar tree, Indian ash, shingle tree

The heartwood is pale pinkish, bright red to reddish brown with darker streaks, distinctly demarcated from the pale yellowish sapwood. The grain is straight to slightly interlocked, sometimes wavy, texture coarse and even. The wood is lustrous. The wood is medium-weight with a density of 520 to 700 kg/m³

Uses: The wood is suitable for indoor construction, furniture, fence posts, beehives, boxes, packing cases, roof shingles, veneer and plywood. The wood is used to produce pulp for paper, but is rated as second-class for that purpose.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Pinus caribaea. Caribbean pine, Pitch pine, Honduran yellow pine, or simply pine

The heartwood is yellowish to reddish brown and distinctly demarcated from the white or yellowish sapwood. The grain is straight, texture medium to coarse, with a density varying from 350 to 560 kg/m³.

Uses: Construction, inexpensive furniture, boxes, pallets, poles, veneer, plywood, particle board and fibre board..

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Pinus patula. Patula pine, Mexican weeping pine, or simply pine

The heartwood is pinkish to creamy white, and not clearly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, spiral or wavy, texture fine. The density is between 430 and 650 kg/m³

Uses: Light construction, boxes, light flooring, joinery, ceilings, panelling, furniture, cabinet work, fence posts, poles pallets, veneer, particle board and plywood.

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Pinus radiata. Radiata pine, Monterey pine, Californian pine, or simply pine

The heartwood is pinkish brown and distinctly demarcated from the exceptionally wide creamy white sapwood, which constitutes the bulk of the commercial timber. The grain is often spiralled near the pith, but elsewhere usually straight, texture moderately fine and even.

The density of the wood can be between 380 to 610 kg/m³.

Uses: Pulp and Paper, construction, joinery, furniture, veneer, plywood, packing cases, poles, posts, shuttering, particle board and fibreboard, and sometimes for flooring, interior trim, toys, turnery, matches, hardboard and wood-wool.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Cupressus lusitanica. East African cypress, or simply cypress

The heartwood is yellowish, pale brown or pinkish, sometimes streaked or variegated; the sapwood is paler and 3-7.5 cm wide. The wood becomes paler on exposure. The grain is straight to irregular, texture fine and even. The density is between 380 and 545 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, furniture, poles and posts, light flooring, boat building, agricultural implements, boxes and crates, interior trim, joinery, toys, turnery, veneer and plywood, hardboard and particle board.

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INDIGENOUS PLANTATION AND NATURAL FORESTS SPECIES

Juniperus procera. East African cedar, African Pencil Cedar. Mutarakwa, Mwangati (Sw)

The heartwood is pale red, yellow-brown or purple-red when freshly cut, turning reddish brown on exposure; it is well demarcated from the cream-coloured or white sapwood. The grain is usually straight, texture fine and even. The wood is very fragrant, with a characteristic and persistent aromatic cedar smell. Ingrown bark, spiral grain and compression wood are common defects. The wood is liable to bleach in the sun and is sometimes streaked with zones of darker and lighter colour, which produce an attractive figure. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 510 to 670 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, joinery, flooring (strip and parquet), furniture, roofing shingles, fence posts, water flumes, transmission poles. Beehives, salt-troughs. manufacture of pencils and penholders, boat building, agricultural implements, musical instruments, carving, vats, toys, turnery, draining boards, food containers, veneer and plywood, hardboard, particle board, and pulpwood.

Acacia robusta. Splendid thorn, Splendid acacia, Ankle thorn. Mgunga (Sw).

The heartwood is pinkish brown to reddish brown and distinctly demarcated from the wide whitish sapwood. The texture is moderately coarse to coarse and even. The wood is moderately heavy, with a density of about 850 kg/m³

Uses: The wood is occasionally used for furniture, shelves and yokes, although its use is limited because of considerable warping.

Acacia xanthophloea. Fever tree, Sulphur bark, African thorn acacia. Mukonge (Sw)

The heartwood is pale brown with a reddish tinge and distinctly demarcated from the wide, paler sapwood. It is fairly heavy, with a density of about 900 kg/m³

Uses: General-purpose timber, which is used in construction and for carpentry, boat building, boxwood, furniture, mortars, domestic utensils, troughs and fence poles.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Afrocarpus falcatus. Yellowwood, African fern pine, weeping yew.

The heartwood is pale yellow to pale yellowish brown, and not distinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, occasionally spirally, texture fine and even. Reddish streaks of compression wood and darker lines resulting from year rings may be present. The wood is moderately lightweight, with a density of 430 to 560 kg/m³

Uses: The wood, often traded as 'podo' or 'yellowwood', is highly valued for ship building, (masts and planks), but it is also used for poles, panelling, furniture, boxes, veneer and plywood, construction, flooring, joinery, interior trim, vehicle bodies, railway sleepers, toys, agricultural implements, musical instruments, food containers, vats, turnery, hardboard and particle board.

Azelia africana. African oak. Mbarika (Sw)

The heartwood is orange-brown to golden brown, becoming red-brown upon prolonged exposure, sometimes with darker streaks. It is distinctly demarcated from the whitish to pale yellow, up to 8 cm wide sapwood. The grain is usually straight, occasionally interlocked, texture medium to coarse but even. The wood is slightly glossy, medium-weight to moderately heavy, with a density of 720 to 850 kg/m³.

Uses: Pleasure crafts, keels, stems and panels, bridges, interior fittings. Joinery, panelling, exterior decking, floors, doors, frames, stairs, furniture, sporting goods. domestic articles such as boxes, bowls, spoons, mortars and drums.

Azelia quanzensis. Rhodesian mahogany. Mkonge (Sw)

The heartwood is yellowish brown to pinkish brown, becoming red-brown upon prolonged exposure, sometimes with darker streaks. It is distinctly demarcated from the whitish to pale

yellow, up to 10 cm wide sapwood. The grain is straight to interlocked, texture coarse but even. The wood is rather heavy, with a density of 800 to 870 kg/m³

Uses: Pleasure-crafts, boat keels, stems and panels, bridges, interior fittings, musical instruments, joinery, panelling, parquet floors, doors, frames, stairs, vehicle bodies, furniture, sporting goods, toys, railway sleepers, agricultural implements, utensils, tool handles, draining boards, carving, turnery, fibre board, particle board,. decorative sliced veneer, vats and precision equipment in industrial applications.

Albizia adianthifolia. Rough-bark, Flat-crown. Mchapia tumbili (Sw).

The heartwood is pale brown or golden brown, sometimes with a greenish tinge, and distinctly demarcated from wide whitish or pale yellow sapwood. The grain is straight or interlocked, texture moderately coarse to coarse. The wood is moderately light, with a density of 520–580 kg/m³

Uses: The wood of *Albizia adianthifolia* is used for light construction (e.g. posts, rafters), carving, light flooring, joinery, interior trim, furniture, cabinet work, boat building, toys, tool handles, baseball bats, boxes, crates, hardboard and particle board.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Albizia glaberrima. White nongo. Mgelenge (Sw).

The heartwood varies from dirty white to reddish brown, sometimes with darker stripes, and is distinctly demarcated from the white sapwood. The grain is straight, sometimes interlocked, texture moderately coarse. The wood is moderately heavy, with a density of about 660 kg/m³

Uses: Furniture, construction, stools, beehives, tool handles, grain mortars, doors, light and heavy flooring, interior trim, joinery, boatbuilding, railway sleepers, toys, boxes, crates, carving and plywood making.

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Albizia gummifera. Peacock flower. Red nongo. Mpepe, Omulera (Sw).

The heartwood is yellowish brown or reddish brown, often with a golden tinge, and distinctly demarcated from the pale yellow or white sapwood. The grain is straight or interlocked, texture medium to coarse. Quarter-sawn surfaces are often striped. The wood is moderately light to moderately heavy, 430 to 800 kg/m³

Uses: Light construction, furniture, cabinet work, various implements. light flooring, joinery, interior trim, panelling, framing, toys, sporting goods, boxes, crates, carvings, peeled and sliced veneer, plywood, hardboard and particle board, pulp is suitable for paper production. Logs were traditionally used for the construction of canoes.

Albizia versicolor. Poison-pod albizia. Mchani, Mduyasi (Sw).

The heartwood is pale to purplish brown, often darker striped, sometimes almost black; it is distinctly demarcated from the white sapwood,. The grain is wavy or interlocked, texture coarse. The wood is moderately heavy, with a density of 560 to 770 kg/m³

Uses: The Boats construction, tool handles, mortars and other kitchen implements, containers, casks and musical instruments. Suitable for light construction, light flooring, joinery, furniture, cabinet work, decorative work, veneer, plywood, draining boards, hardboard and particle board

Antiaris toxicaria. Antiaris, bark cloth tree, false iroko. Mkunde (Sw).

Heartwood whitish to pale yellow or pale yellow-brown, indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is interlocked, texture moderately coarse. The wood has a ribbon-like aspect on quarter-sawn faces, and is lustrous. Fresh wood has woolly surfaces.

Density: 370 to 480 kg/m³

Uses: Light construction, interior joinery, panelling, moulding, shuttering, furniture, strip flooring, boxes and crates, drums, tool handles, toys, carvings, peeled and sliced, fibre and particle board and blockboard.

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Anthocleista grandiflora. Cabbage tree, forest fever tree, forest big-leaf. Mutunguru (Sw).

The heartwood is white or pale brown and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, sometimes spirally, texture medium to coarse. Radial surfaces show a stripe or ribbon figure. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 580 to 640 kg/m³

Uses: Light construction, light flooring, joinery, interior trim, furniture, crates, boxes, carvings and vats. Suitable for veneer, plywood, hardboard, particle board and pulpwood.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Apodytes dimidiata. White pear, pear wood. Mlambusi, Mbage (Sw).

The heartwood is pale grey to brownish grey or nearly white, with brownish patches, darker near the centre of the log; it is not clearly demarcated from the thin sapwood. The grain is straight, texture fine and even. The wood is fairly heavy, with a density of 720 to 900 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, flooring, furniture, agricultural implements, carving and turnery, carts, interior trim, boat building, musical instruments, toys, and precision equipment.

Bivinia jalbertii. Cobweb tree

The heartwood is yellowish white and indistinctly demarcated from the up to 5 cm wide sapwood.

The wood medium-weight, with a density of 700 to 810 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, poles and posts, bridges and hydraulic works, heavy-duty flooring, indoor and outdoor joinery, interior trim, boat building, ladders, sporting goods, railway sleepers, toys, tool handles, boxes and crates.

Brachylaena hutchinsii (Brachylaena huillensis). Silver oak, silky oak. Muhugu, Muhuhu (Sw)

The heartwood is grayish-yellow to yellowish-brown or greenish-brown and distinctly demarcated from the creamy-white to grayish-white sapwood. The grain is straight to interlocked, texture fine and even. The wood has a persistent spicy odour. Quarter-sawn surfaces have a faint stripe figure. The wood is heavy with a density of 830 to 990 kg/m³

Uses: The Construction, first-grade flooring, joinery, interior trim, furniture, fence posts, toys, boxes, crates, tool handles, carving and turnery, bridges, hydraulic works, poles, cabinet work and railway sleepers.

Brachystegia spiciformis. Bean-pod tree. Myombo, Mrihi (Sw).

The heartwood is variable in colour, from pale brown to reddish brown, darkening on exposure, sometimes striped, and clearly demarcated from the pale cream to white sapwood. The grain is interlocked, texture coarse, with a density of 680 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, door frames, canoes, cheap furniture, railway sleepers (if treated), utensils and beehives., flooring, joinery, interior trim, boxes, crates, food containers, veneer, plywood and pulp for paper.

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Calodendrum capense. Cape chestnut

The heartwood is whitish to straw-coloured, occasionally with greenish or brownish markings, and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, texture fine to medium. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 610 to 740 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, poles, furniture, grain mortars, tool handles, implements and yokes, flooring, joinery, boats, sporting goods, toys, musical instruments, boxes, railway sleepers, turnery, and suitable for veneer, plywood and pulpwood.

Calophyllum inophyllum. Alexandrian laurel, beauty leaf. Motondoo (Sw).

The heartwood is pinkish to reddish brown, and clearly demarcated from the pale sapwood. The grain is interlocked, spiral or wavy, texture moderately coarse and uneven. Planed surface lustrous; stripe figure present on radial surface and darker coloured zigzag markings on tangential surface. The wood is medium-weight to moderately heavy, with a density of 560 to 800 kg/m³

Uses: Throughout its area of distribution the wood has been used for the construction of canoes and boats, and also for masts, keels, knees ribs and cheek and pulley blocks.. Also used in construction, carpentry, flooring, stairs, furniture and cabinet work, cart-wheel hubs, vessels and musical instruments.

Casearia battiscombei. Forest sword-leaf. Muirungi (Sw)

The heartwood is restricted to a narrow dark brown core, sapwood very wide, whitish to pale yellow-brown, sometimes with reddish streaks. The grain is straight, texture fine and even. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 515 to 750 kg/m³

Uses: Joinery, interior trim and furniture. Suitable for boxes, crates, turnery, veneer and plywood, and as pulpwood for paper production..

Cassipourea ruwensoriensis.

The heartwood is whitish with mauve markings in the core, and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, texture fine and even. The density is 810 to 900 kg/m³

Uses: Light construction, ship and boat building, furniture and cabinet work, musical instruments, boxes and crates, interior trim, toys, turnery, and suitable for veneer, plywood, hardboard and particle board.

Cassipourea eurvoidea. Mugome, Ngome (Sw).

The heartwood is creamy white with purplish streaks and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, texture fine and even. The density is about 850 kg/m³

Uses: Heavy construction, flooring, ship and boat building, furniture, cabinet work, interior trim, joinery, poles and piles, implements, toys, turnery, carving, and veneer and plywood.

Cassipourea gummiflua. Large-leaved onion wood, broad-leaved onion wood. Msikundazi (Sw).

The heartwood is greyish or yellowish white and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, texture moderately fine and even. The wood has a density of 480 to 720 kg/m³

Uses: The General purpose timber, suitable for light construction, poles, masts, flooring, furniture and cabinet work, handles, ladders, boxes and crates, interior trim, implements, joinery, toys, turnery, suitable for veneer, plywood, hardboard and particle board.

Cassipourea malosana. Pillarwood. Musaisi (Sw)

The heartwood varies in colour, from whitish to brown, often with purple streaks associated with fungal attack; it is indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is usually straight, but with a slight to marked tendency to spiralling; texture fine and even. Freshly cut wood smells like onion. The wood has a density of 600 to 840 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, heavy duty or industrial flooring, furniture and cabinet work, tool handles, ladders, sporting goods, agricultural implements, joinery, sleepers, poles and posts, toys, beehives, turnery, veneer and plywood

Celtis gomphophylla. Bastard white stinkwood, Forest celtis. Ohia (Sw)

The heartwood is whitish, turning slightly darker upon exposure, and not distinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is usually interlocked, texture moderately fine. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 510 to 600 kg/m³

Uses: Light construction, light flooring, joinery, furniture, cabinet work, canoes, ladders, sporting goods, agricultural implements, tool handles and matches. Also suitable for hardboard and particle board.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Celtis mildbraedii. Red-fruited white stinkwood. Mokolongo, Mokalungo (Sw).

The heartwood is white to pale yellow or greenish, darkening upon exposure to greyish white, and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is often interlocked, sometimes straight, texture rather fine and even. Surfaces are often lustrous. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 600 to 785 kg/m³

Uses: Poles and posts, tool handles, spoons, construction, flooring, joinery, interior trim, railway sleepers, boat building, furniture, ladders, sporting goods, boxes, crates, agricultural implements, veneer, plywood, hardboard and particle board.

Cephalosphaera usambarensis. Mtambao, Mtambara (Sw).

The heartwood is pale reddish brown and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is usually straight, texture medium. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 510 to 650 kg/m³

Uses: The Veneer and plywood, light construction, light flooring, joinery, interior trim, furniture, toys, agricultural implements, boxes, crates, carving, turnery, matches, hardboard, particle board and pulpwood.

Combretum schumannii. Forest tree combretum, Sand bushwillow. Mgururue (Sw).

The heartwood is dark purplish brown when freshly sawn, slowly darkening to nearly black after years, and distinctly demarcated from the narrow, whitish sapwood. The grain is straight, texture moderately fine to fine, but not always even. The wood is heavy, with a density of 1040 to 1120 kg/m³

Uses: Heavy construction, flooring, pestles, combs and carvings, interior trim, boat building, vehicle bodies, handles, ladders, sporting goods, musical instruments, pulley blocks, toys, precision equipment and turnery.

Cordyla Africana. East African Cordyla, Wild mango, Bush mango, Sunbird tree. Makobokobo, Mumbwe (Sw).

The heartwood is yellowish brown to brown, with darker bands, and fairly distinctly demarcated from the paler wide sapwood. The grain is wavy or interlocked, texture coarse. It has a nice figure due to wavy stripes. The wood is medium-weight to heavy, with a density of 750 to 910 kg/m³

Uses: The wood is used for heavy construction, bridge decking, furniture, tool handles, household utensils, beehives and carvings, medium-heavy flooring, joinery, interior trim, boat building, vehicle bodies, railway sleepers, toys, and drums.

Cordia abyssinica-Cordia Africana. Large-leaved cordia, East African cordia, Sudan teak, Cordia. Mukumari, Makobokobo (Sw).

The heartwood is pinkish brown to reddish brown and fairly distinctly demarcated from the greyish sapwood. The grain is usually interlocked, texture medium to coarse but even. The wood is lustrous, moderately lightweight, with a density of 440 to 580 kg/m³

Uses: Joinery, interior trim, panelling, furniture, cabinet work, drums, beehives, boxes, mortars, light construction, boat building, vehicle bodies, toys, vats, draining boards, food containers veneer, plywood, hardboard, particle board and gum production

Cordia subcordata. Sea trumpet, Beach cordial, Island walnut

The heartwood is pale brown to dark brown, often with a purplish tinge and dark brown to nearly black streaks, and distinctly demarcated from the pale yellowish brown sapwood. The grain is usually interlocked, texture moderately fine. The wood is rather glossy. It is moderately lightweight, with a density of 470 to 650 kg/m³

Uses: Light construction, beams and posts, furniture, cabinet making, musical instruments, tools, utensils, boxes, carvings, fancy articles, and sliced veneer.

Cordia millenii. African cordia, Drum tree. Mringamringa (Sw)

The heartwood is pale brown to yellowish brown or medium brown, occasionally pale purplish or pinkish brown, and not distinctly demarcated from the whitish or yellowish, 4–6 cm wide sapwood. The grain is straight or interlocked, often producing a stripe figure, texture medium to coarse. The wood is moderately lightweight, with a density of 410 to 500 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, joinery, interior trim, panelling, furniture, musical instruments including drums, boxes, toys, utensils, tool handles, shingles, boat building, veneer, plywood and carving..

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Croton megalocarpus. Croton. Musine (Sw)

The heartwood is yellowish white to brownish grey, often with irregular dark brown streaks, and not distinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is usually straight, texture medium. Freshly sawn wood has an unpleasant smell. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 700 to 750 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, flooring, furniture, mortars, beehives, veneer, plywood, joinery, interior trim, boat building, railway sleepers and agricultural implements.

Cussonia zimmermannii. Mbomba maji, Mpapayi mwitu (Sw).

The heartwood is whitish and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The texture is moderately fine. The wood is lightweight, with a density of about 400 kg/m³

Uses: Coffins, drums, boats, carvings, furniture and light interior construction.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Dalbergia melanoxylon. East African Blackwood, African blackwood, Zebra wood African ebony, African grenadillo, African ironwood. Mpingo (Sw).

The heartwood is very dark brown to purplish black, sometimes with black streaks, and sharply demarcated from the yellowish white thin sapwood. The grain is straight, texture very fine and even. The wood has an oily surface. The wood is very heavy; the sapwood has a density of about 1180 kg/m³ and the heartwood of 1230 to 1330 kg/m³

Uses: The heartwood of *Dalbergia melanoxylon* was already used by the ancient Egyptians for artefacts and for furniture such as thrones and beds.

Locally: Carvings, marquetry and utensils including precision equipment, musical instruments, especially wind-instruments such as clarinets, oboes, flutes and bagpipes, because of its dark colour, stability and clearness of tone. Violin-makers use it for the fingerboard, tailpiece, chinrest, scrolls and button, turning, parquet flooring, rafters, poles in construction, walking sticks, drumsticks, arrow tips, pestles, cups, plates and combs.

Diospyros abyssinica. Diospyros spp. Ebony, Black bark. Mueluili, Mdaa-mwitu (Sw).

The heartwood is whitish yellow to pale grey-brown, often with irregular black streaks or entirely black in the centre; it is not distinctly demarcated from the wide, whitish to yellowish sapwood.

The grain is generally straight, sometimes interlocked, texture usually fine. Freshly cut wood has an unpleasant smell. The wood is hard, tough and moderately heavy with a density of 720 to 860 kg/m³

Uses: Heavy flooring, poles, interior trim, furniture, cabinet making, masts of dhows, agricultural implements, musical instruments, tool handles, ladders, toys, pestles and mortars, golf club heads, walking sticks, carving and turnery, loom shuttles in weaving sisal cloth Kenya.

Dombeya goezenii. Forest dombeya. Mueko (Sw).

The heartwood is not clearly demarcated from the sapwood. The wood is uniformly pale brown, often with a central core of dark brown wood with olive streaks. The grain is usually straight, texture fine to medium. The density of the wood is 705 kg/m³

Uses: Flooring, boat building, furniture, tool handles, ladders, sporting goods, agricultural implements, yokes, poles, posts, bows and carved traditional stools.

Drypetes gerrardii. Forest ironwood, Forest ironplum. Munyenye (Sw).

The heartwood is whitish, turning pale yellowish to greyish upon exposure, with occasional brownish streaks, and indistinctly demarcated from the wide sapwood. The grain is straight, occasionally slightly interlocked, texture fine and even. The wood is medium-weight to heavy, with a density of 710 to 815 kg/m³

Uses: and Poles in construction, joinery, furniture, tool handles, utensils, flooring, boat building, sporting goods, boxes, crates, agricultural implements and turnery.

Ehretia cymosa

The wood is greyish brown with alternate darker and lighter bands, and lustrous. The texture is moderately fine and even. The wood is moderately lightweight, with a density of 480 to 550 kg/m³

Uses: Furniture, cabinet work, poles, tool handles and yokes.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Ekebergia capensis. Dog plum, Mountain ash. Mpoto wa ndovu mkuu (Sw)

The heartwood is whitish to pale pink when freshly cut, darkening to greyish white, pale pinkish brown or pale brown upon drying. It is indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, texture moderately fine to coarse. Some figure may be present on backsawn surfaces. The wood is medium-weight to moderately heavy, with a density of 495 to 705 kg/m³

Uses: Furniture, light construction, poles, tool handles. light flooring, joinery, interior trim, sporting goods, toys, vats, food containers, boxes, crates, matches, turnery, veneer and plywood.

Elaeodendron buchananii. Elaeodendron.

The heartwood is pale brown to reddish brown and distinctly demarcated from the whitish sapwood. The grain is straight or interlocked, texture moderately fine. The wood is heavy, with a density of about 800 kg/m³

Uses: Joinery and furniture, heavy construction, heavy flooring, interior trim, handles, ladders, sporting goods, toys, turnery, pattern making, veneer and plywood.

Entandrophragma angolense. Tiama mahogany

The heartwood is pale pinkish brown to pale reddish brown, slightly darkening upon exposure to deep reddish brown, and distinctly demarcated from the creamy white to pale pinkish sapwood. The grain is interlocked, texture moderately coarse and fairly even. Quarter-sawn surfaces are irregularly striped. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 510 to 735 kg/m³

Uses: Exterior and interior joinery, furniture, cabinet work, veneer and plywood, flooring, interior trim, panelling, stairs, coffins, light construction, musical instruments, toys, boxes, crates, carvings and turnery.

Fagaropsis angolensis

The heartwood is yellowish grey to dark green or brown tinged with green or yellow, darkening on exposure, and fairly distinctly demarcated from the pale yellow or greenish to greyish white sapwood. The grain is usually straight, occasionally wavy, texture moderately fine and even. The wood is lustrous. Due to variations in colour and grain, the wood sometimes has a beautiful figure on both radial and tangential sections and also on peeled veneer. The wood is moderately heavy, with a density of about 700 kg/m³

Uses: Flooring, furniture, paneling, light construction, joinery, interior trim, sporting goods, toys, musical instruments, carving, turnery, veneer and plywood.

Faurea saligna. Red beech, African beech, African red beech.

Heartwood yellowish brown to pinkish brown or reddish brown and rather indistinctly demarcated from the slightly paler sapwood. The grain is interlocked, texture moderately coarse. The wood has a distinct net-like pattern of darker spots on tangential surfaces, and horizontal bands on radial surfaces. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 720 to 770 kg/m³

Uses: Poles and posts in construction, joinery, panelling, furniture, utensils, ornaments, fence posts, flooring, railway sleepers, toys, tool handles, carvings, turnery, veneer and plywood.

Ficus sur. Wild fig, broom cluster fig, bush fig. Mkuyu, Mkuju (Sw).

The heartwood is white or yellow and not clearly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight or interlocked, texture moderately coarse to coarse. The wood is light with a density 300 to 450 kg/m³.

Uses: Light construction, furniture, kitchen utensils, pots, boxes, beer troughs, drums, beehives, agricultural implements, hardboard and particle board..

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Ficus variifolia. Mvumo (Sw)

The heartwood is whitish yellow or pale yellowish brown, sometimes slightly pinkish; it is not clearly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, texture coarse and even. The density is about 400 kg/m³.

Uses: Carving, joinery, light carpentry, agricultural implements, toys, boxes, crates and matches.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Greenwayodendron suaveolens. Molinda.

The heartwood is yellow to brown when dry and usually not distinctly demarcated from the sapwood, which is yellowish white when freshly cut, but darkening upon exposure. The grain is usually straight, texture variable. Quarter-sawn surfaces show streaky markings. The wood is lustrous, medium weight, with a density of 750 to 790 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, joinery, furniture, rafters, shafts of spears, flooring, interior trim, railway sleepers, toys, agricultural implements, vats, draining boards, food containers, turnery, veneer and plywood.

Heywoodia lucens. Stink ebony.

The heartwood is dark purplish to nearly black, and distinctly demarcated from the narrow sapwood. The grain is usually straight, texture coarse and even. It is heavy, with a density of 780 to 960 kg/m³.

Uses: Poles, agricultural implements, tool handles, wooden spoons, heavy construction, flooring, joinery, interior trim, furniture, railway sleepers, toys, veneer, and musical instruments..

Khaya anthotheca. Smooth-barked mahogany. Mkangazi (Sw)

The heartwood is pinkish brown to deep red and more or less distinctly demarcated from the pale brown, up to 6 cm wide sapwood. The grain is straight or interlocked, texture rather coarse. The wood has an attractive figure with irregular ripple marks. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 490 to 660 kg/m³

Uses: Furniture, cabinet work, decorative boxes and cases, veneer, window and door frames, panelling, doors, staircases, light flooring, boat building, sporting goods, musical instruments, toys, carving, plywood and pulpwood.

Ilex mitis. African holly, Cape holly, watertree. Msaira (Sw).

The heartwood is whitish to pale grey, sometimes greyish green to brownish towards the centre of the log, and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, texture fine. The wood shows a conspicuous silver-grain figure on radial surfaces. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 590 to 690 kg/m³

Uses: Light construction, light flooring, interior trim, boat building, furniture, toys, musical instruments such as drums and guitars, tool handles, agricultural implements, railway sleepers, boxes, crates, vats, beehives, matches, veneer, plywood, hardboard, particle board and pulpwood, buckboards and spokes in wagon construction, heels of ladies shoes.

Lannea welwitschii. Muumbu, Kumbi (Sw).

The heartwood is creamy white to pale brown or pinkish grey and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is usually straight, but occasionally interlocked, texture medium to fine and even. Quarter-sawn surfaces show a streaked or mottled figure. The wood has a silvery luster, and is moderately lightweight to medium-weight, with a density of 400 to 640 kg/m³

Uses: Light joinery, boxes, crates, utensils such as cups, plates, pots and mortars, and for veneer and plywood. The boles were traditionally used to make canoes. Also suitable for light flooring, interior trim, vehicle bodies, furniture, cabinet work, matches, hardboard, particle board and pulpwood..

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Macaranga capensis. River macaranga, Spiny macaranga, Swamp poplar, Wild poplar.. Mkalanga, Mlanga-makelele, Mbawa (Sw).

The heartwood is pink to greyish, with dark brown stripes, and distinctly demarcated from the white, narrow sapwood. The grain is usually straight, texture medium. The wood is lightweight, with a density of 360 to 500 kg/m³

Uses: Light construction, planks, low-grade furniture, boxes, crates, beehives, xylophones, water pots and traditional stools.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Margaritaria discoidea. Common pheasant berry, peacock-berry. Mjangari (Sw).

The heartwood is pinkish white to brownish red, taking a purplish tinge with time, and distinctly demarcated from the pale brown to yellowish sapwood. The grain is straight or slightly interlocked, texture medium to fine. The wood is fairly lustrous, heavy, with a density of 740 to 975 kg/m³

Uses: Poles and posts, planks and shingles in house building, flooring, general carpentry, interior trim, toys, draining boards, boat building, cabinet making, carvings, turnery, veneer and plywood.

Markhamia lutea. Bean tree, Markhamia, Siala. Mgambo (Sw).

The heartwood is straw-coloured to pale brown, slightly darkening upon exposure, and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, texture medium and even.

The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 560 to 575 kg/m³

Uses: Light construction, poles, posts, joinery, furniture, cabinet work, walking sticks, beehives, paddles, tool handles, props for crops, light flooring, interior trim, sporting goods, toys, boxes, crates, matches, turnery, veneer, plywood, pulpwood, fermentation tanks, tubs, barrels, door and window frames.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Myrsine melanophloeos. Cape beech

The heartwood is whitish to pale brown or pinkish brown, darkening upon exposure, and indistinctly demarcated from the wide sapwood. The grain is straight, sometimes with a tendency to wavy, texture medium to fine and even. Quarter-sawn surfaces show a nice silver-grain figure, and backsawn surfaces show a reticulated-mottled pattern.

The wood is medium-weight to heavy, with a density of 680 to 845 kg/m³

Uses: The wood is used for joinery, decorative panelling, poles, furniture, cabinet work, musical instruments such as violins, carved sticks, implements and tool handles, construction, flooring, interior trim, railway sleepers, toys, pattern making, carvings, turnery, veneer and plywood.

Milicia excelsa. Iroko, Rock elm, African teak, African oak. Mvule (Sw).

The heartwood is pale yellow to yellow, darkening on exposure to yellowish or greenish brown or sometimes to chocolate brown; it is clearly demarcated from the yellowish white sapwood. The grain is interlocked, texture medium to coarse, figure mottled. The wood is somewhat greasy, with a density of 550 to 750 kg/m³

Uses: Construction work, shipbuilding and marine carpentry, sleepers, sluice gates, framework, trucks, draining boards, outdoor and indoor joinery, stairs, doors, frames, garden furniture, cabinet work, panelling, flooring and profile boards for decorative and structural uses, carving, domestic utensils, musical instruments, toys, tanks and barrels for food and chemical products, for laboratory benches. And sliced veneer

Nectaropetalum kaessneri. Mfunda mweupe (Sw).

The heartwood is orange or golden yellow, darkening upon exposure, and distinctly demarcated from the white to pale yellow, pink or grey sapwood. The grain is usually interlocked or irregular, texture moderately coarse to coarse. The wood is lustrous, and quarter-sawn surfaces have a streaked figure. The wood is medium-weight to heavy, with a density of 670 to 910 kg/m³

Uses: Poles in house building, tool handles, carving, mortars, furniture and drums.

Neoboutonia macrocalyx.

The heartwood is white to grey-white, often with irregular dark brown streaks, and not distinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, texture coarse. The wood is lightweight, with a density of 350 to 390 kg/m³

Uses: House construction, carving, inner parts of plywood, boxes, crates, stools, water pots and beehives..

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Nesogordonia holtzii. Muheru, Mrunza (Sw)

Moderately heavy, hard and tough. The heartwood is pale pink to brown, distinctly demarcated from the paler sapwood. The grain is straight, texture fine. The wood surface is lustrous and greasy. The density is 810 to 900 kg/m³.

Uses: Poles, sawn timber in house building, turning, and veneer.

Newtonia buchananii. East African newtonia, Forest newtonia. Mnyassa (Sw).

The heartwood is pale brown, darkening to golden brown upon exposure, distinctly demarcated from the greyish white sapwood. The grain is interlocked, texture moderately coarse to coarse. The

wood has some stripe or ribbon figure and is lustrous, medium-weight with a density is 560 to 670 kg/m³.

Uses: Tool handles, implements, carpentry, joinery, cabinet work, doors, door frames, bridges, boat building, fencing, light construction, flooring, interior trim, boxes, crates, veneer and plywood. It was used traditionally to make dugout canoes.

Ochna holstii. Red ironwood, Real red pear, Common forest ochna. Mkamachuma (Sw).

The properties given refer to wood of several Ochna species, including that of *Ochna holstii*. The heartwood is pale red-brown and distinctly demarcated from the narrow, pale yellow sapwood. The grain is straight, texture fine and even. The wood is heavy, with a density of 880 to 950 kg/m³

Uses: Joinery, furniture, domestic utensils, tool handles, heavy construction, heavy flooring, interior trim, ship building, sporting goods, toys, musical instruments, precision instruments, agricultural implements, carving, turnery, pattern making, sliced veneer and plywood.

Ocotea usambarensis. East African camphor wood. Mkulo (Sw)

The heartwood is pale yellowish brown when freshly cut, darkening to deep brown upon exposure, and sometimes lustrous; it is not distinctly demarcated from the slightly paler sapwood. The grain is usually interlocked, texture even and moderately fine to fine. Quarter-sawn surfaces show a stripe or ribbon figure. The wood has a distinct camphor-like smell, medium-weight, with a density of 450 kg/m³

Uses: Joinery, panelling, poles and posts, doors, window frames, shutters, furniture, cabinet work, flooring, construction, boat building, boxes, crates, vats, matches, sliced veneer, plywood pulpwood.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Ocotea kenyensis. Northern stinkwood. Mkulo (Sw)

The heartwood is pale golden brown to dark brown, with blackish markings; it is lustrous. The grain is often wavy, texture moderately fine. The wood is moderately heavy, with a density of about 750 kg/m³ at 12% moisture content.

Uses: Flooring, panelling, furniture, carving, light construction, joinery, interior trim, handles, ladders, sporting goods, toys, turnery, veneer and plywood.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Olea europaea (Var. Africana). Wild Olive, Brown olive. Mutero (Sw)

The heartwood is pale brown to dark brown, often with irregular grey-black or yellowish streaks. It is distinctly demarcated from the yellowish white to grey sapwood. The grain is straight to slightly interlocked, texture fine and even. The wood surface shows a nice figure and is slightly oily to the touch. The wood is heavy, with a density of 860 to 975 kg/m³

Uses: The timber is highly prized for fancy furniture, cabinets, carving wood, turnery, flooring, carpentry, panelling, house and bridge construction, counter and table tops, railway sleepers, tool handles, wagon parts, sliced veneer, sports goods, and toys.

Olea capensis. Elgon teak, Elgon olive. Musharagi (Sw)

The heartwood is pale brown to dark brown, often with irregular grey-black or yellowish streaks. It is distinctly demarcated from the yellowish white to grey sapwood. The grain is straight to slightly interlocked, texture fine and even. The wood surface shows a nice figure and is slightly oily to the touch. The wood is heavy, with a density of 860 to 975 kg/m³

Uses: Furniture, heavy construction, flooring, carpentry, panelling, house and bridge construction, counter and table tops, railway sleepers, tool handles and wagon parts, turnery, interior trim, carving, sporting goods, toys, agricultural implements. and sliced veneer. The bark of the tree has medicinal properties.

Olea hochstetteri. East African olive, Iron wood, Elgon olive. Mushargi (Sw)

The heartwood is pale brown to dark brown, often with irregular grey-black or yellowish streaks. It is distinctly demarcated from the yellowish white to grey sapwood. The grain is straight to slightly interlocked, texture fine and even. The wood surface shows a nice figure and is slightly oily to the touch. The wood is heavy, with a density of 860 to 975 kg/m³

Uses: Furniture, flooring, carpentry, wood spokes, tool handles, paneling, turning, house and bridge construction, counter and table tops, railway sleepers, tool handles and wagon parts. sliced veneer, porting goods, toys, and agricultural implements..

Paramacrolobium coeruleum. Mkwe (Sw).

The heartwood is pale brown to yellowish brown or pinkish brown with darker brown streaks on quarter-sawn surfaces, and usually indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight to interlocked, texture moderately coarse and even. The wood is moderately heavy, with a density of about 700 kg/m³

Uses: Joinery, doors, frames of doors, furniture, railway sleepers, heavy flooring, interior trim, toys, turnery, carving, veneer and plywood.

Parinari excelsa. Grey plum, Guinea plum, Rough-skinned plum. Mubura (Sw)

The heartwood is yellowish brown, darkening upon exposure to deep red or chocolate brown, and not clearly demarcated from the yellowish white sapwood. The grain is wavy to interlocked, texture moderately coarse to coarse. The wood is heavy, with a density of 730 to 920 kg/m³

Uses: Heavy construction, hydraulic works in sea water, heavy-duty flooring, poles, piles, joinery, interior trim, furniture, ladders, sporting goods, agricultural implements, tool handles, veneer, plywood, block-board, railway sleepers.

Podocarpus latifolius. Podo. Musengera (Sw)

The heartwood is pale yellowish brown, and not demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, occasionally spirally, texture fine and even. Reddish streaks of compression wood may be present. The wood has no distinctive (podo) odour, with a density of between 460 and 510 kg/m³

Uses: Highly valued for furniture and ship building, e.g. for masts and planks. Also used for poles, panelling, boxes, veneer and plywood, butchers' blocks, construction, flooring, joinery, interior trim, railway sleepers, toys, agricultural implements, musical instruments, coffins, food containers, vats, carving, pattern making, matches, turnery, hardboard and particle board. and high-quality pulpwood.

Prunus africanum. African plum, African cherry, Red stinkwood, Bitter almond. Mueni (Sw)

The sapwood is pink in colour, whereas the heartwood is deep-red in colour. The wood is heavy, straight-grained, with a density of 580 to 640 kg/m³

Uses: Manufacture of furniture, axe and hoe handles, utensils, wagons, floors, chopping blocks, carving, bridge decks, railway sleepers, bridges and lorry bodies, door frames, and mortars and pestles.

The bark is probably the most valuable part of the tree because of its pharmaceutical importance in cancer curing drugs.

Polyscias fulva. Parasol tree. Mutati (Sw)

The heartwood is whitish to pale yellow-brown, and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The wood is soft and brittle. The grain is usually straight, texture moderately fine to rather coarse. The wood is lightweight, with a density of 330 to 450 kg/m³.

Uses: Interior joinery, doors, utensils, musical instruments, containers, boxes, crates, beehives, carvings, matches, veneer and plywood. Fuelwood and Charcoal.

****Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications**

Populus ilicifolia. Tana River poplar.

The wood is brown, with a coarse texture. It is lightweight, with a density of about 500 kg/m³

Uses: Poles, posts, utensils, beehives. plywood, dug-out canoes

****Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications**

Premna maxima. Musalengue (Sw)

The heartwood of *Premna maxima* is grey-brown or grey tinged with green, and not clearly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, texture medium and even. The density of the wood is 560 to 740 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, poles and posts, light flooring, boat building, furniture and cabinet work, joinery, toys, agricultural implements, boxes and crates, vats, turnery, draining boards, food containers, veneer and plywood.

Psydrax parviflora

The heartwood is pale brown to dark brown, often with a purplish tinge, and indistinctly demarcated from the paler sapwood. The grain is straight, texture fine and even. The wood is moderately heavy, with a density of 720 to 800 kg/m³

Uses: Joinery, interior trim, furniture, boat construction, general construction, flooring, railway sleepers, ladders, sporting goods, agricultural implements, tool handles, draining boards, pattern making, turnery, veneer and plywood.

Ptaeroxylon obliquum. Sneezewood. Mwandara (Sw).

The heartwood is rose-red to dark red, changing to orange-brown or golden brown on exposure, and distinctly demarcated from the pale grey, narrow sapwood. The grain is wavy, texture fine. The wood has a satiny luster, containing oil that makes it very inflammable.

The wood is heavy, with a density of about 1000 kg/m³

Uses: Furniture, construction poles, keys of traditional xylophones, railway sleepers, durable fence posts. heavy construction including marine works, heavy flooring, vehicle bodies, handles, sporting goods, implements, toys, precision equipment, carving, pattern making, vats and turnery.

Pterocarpus angolensis. African bloodwood. Mninga (Sw)

The heartwood is pale to dark brown or reddish brown, often with streaks, and distinctly demarcated from the pale grey or pale yellow sapwood. The grain is straight to interlocked, texture medium to coarse. The wood is relatively light, the density is 400 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, carpentry, furniture manufacture, doors and windows, parquet flooring, wood carving, bowls, spoons and walking sticks, boat-building and veneer.

Pterocarpus tinctorius. Mninga maji (Sw).

The heartwood is pale yellow when freshly cut but turning to pinkish red upon exposure, and distinctly demarcated from the whitish sapwood. The grain is often interlocked, texture moderately fine. Irregular, small, dark red or brown markings are present on tangential surfaces. The density of the wood ranges from about 450 kg/m³ (forest trees) to about 900 kg/m³ (savanna trees)

Uses: Furniture, cabinet making, decorative parquet floors, light construction, joinery, interior trim, boxes, crates, tool handles, carving, turnery, veneer, plywood, hardboard, particle board, and pulpwood for lower-quality paper production.

Pycnanthus angolensis. **Pycnanthus kombo**. African nutmeg, Boxboard. Mkungu mwitu (Sw).

The heartwood is whitish to pinkish brown, sometimes with yellowish markings and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is generally straight, the texture medium to coarse. At 12% moisture the density is 440 to 570 kg/m³

Uses: Shingles for roofing and exterior wall covering, door and window frames, plywood corestock, veneer, mouldings, interior trim, interior joinery, furniture components and paper pulp. The long straight bole makes it suitable for making dug out canoes.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Quassia undulata. Mjoho (Sw)

The heartwood is greyish white to pale yellow, somewhat lustrous, and is not clearly differentiated from the sapwood. The grain is usually straight, sometimes interlocked, texture medium to coarse and even. Fine striations are present on quarter-sawn surfaces. The wood is lightweight, with a density of 290 to 450 kg/m³

Uses: Interior construction shipping crates to transport easily bruised or breakable products, such as machinery and fruit, because of its softness. Also suitable for veneer, plywood and modelling. Locally used for house construction, planks, doors, ceilings, carpentry, musical instruments, toys, stools, carvings, troughs and canoes.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Rhodognaphalon schumannianum. East African bombax, Wild kapok tree. Msufi mwitu, Msufi pori (Sw).

The heartwood is pale to dark pinkish brown with diffuse dark bands; it is indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood when freshly cut, but on drying the approximately 7.5 cm wide sapwood becomes cream-coloured. The grain is straight, texture medium to moderately coarse. The density of the wood varies from 420 to 580 kg/m³

Uses: Roofing, doors, paneling, low-grade plywood for packing cases, low-grade furniture, sporting goods, matches, hardboard, particle board, wood-wool, pulping, and traditional dugout canoes..

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Schefflera abyssinica

The heartwood is yellowish brown and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The texture is coarse. The wood is lightweight, with a density of about 460 kg/m³

Uses: Furniture, boxes, agricultural implements, inner layers of plywood.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Schrebera alata.

The heartwood is whitish to pale brown, often with slightly darker streaks, not distinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight to slightly wavy, texture fine and even. The wood is moderately heavy, with a density of 780–835 kg/m³.

Uses: Construction, house building, poles, furniture, tool handles, flooring, joinery, interior trim, toys, agricultural implements, turnery, pattern making, veneer and plywood.

Sideroxylon inerme. White milkwood. Mchocha mwitu (Sw)

The wood is yellowish brown with a fine texture. It is heavy, with a density of 1040 kg/m³

Uses: Poles. Posts, heavy construction, boat building, bridges, railway sleepers milled parts..

Spirostachys africana. Spirostahys spp. African sandalwood. Msarakana (Sw).

The heartwood is brown to dark brown with darker markings and streaks, and distinctly demarcated from the whitish to pale yellow sapwood. The grain is straight to slightly wavy, texture moderately fine to fine, and even. The wood has a beautiful banded figure and a satin-like lustre, with an oily surface. It has a fragrant, spicy smell, resembling that of East Indian sandalwood (*Santalum album* L.), which can persist for many years. The wood is very heavy, with a density of 910 to 1090 kg/m³

Uses: The wood is in high demand for decorative joinery, furniture and cabinet work, carvings and turnery. Also used in house construction for posts, beams and roof laths, and to make scented beads for necklaces. Suitable for heavy flooring, ship building, toys, agricultural implements and musical instruments.

Stadmannia oppositifolia. Iron wood, Bourbon iron wood, Silky plum. Mfundu (Sw).

The wood is pinkish to pale red, hard and tough. It is heavy, with a density of 890–1020 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, boats, furniture, carving.

Strombosia scheffleri. Strombosia. Msangana (Sw).

The heartwood is pale reddish brown, darkening upon exposure, and indistinctly demarcated by a pinkish intermediate zone from the whitish cream sapwood. The grain is fairly straight, sometimes wavy, texture medium to fine and even. The wood is fairly lustrous, with a density of 800 to 1010 kg/m³

Uses: Heavy construction, poles, carpentry, furniture, mortars, heavy-duty flooring, interior trim, vehicle bodies, railway sleepers, sporting goods, ladders, toys, utensils, tool handles, turnery and Ground wood chips for the manufacture of cement particle boards.

Strychnos mitis-Strychnos spp. Pitted-leaf Strychnos, Hard pear. Mtonga, Mwangajini mdogo, Mlyaminga (Sw)

The heartwood is pale grey to cream, yellow or pale brown with conspicuous white streaks, and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight or interlocked, texture coarse. The wood is heavy, with a density of 860 to 990 kg/m³

Uses: Building poles, railway sleepers, tool handles, flooring, joinery, interior trim, ship building, vehicle bodies, furniture, sporting goods, toys, agricultural implements and turnery.

Symphonia globulifera. Boarwood, Hog gum, Chew stick. Mziwaziwa (Sw).

The heartwood is buff-brown with shades of yellow, rose or orange, and distinctly demarcated from the grey-yellow sapwood. The grain is generally straight, sometimes interlocked, texture medium to coarse. The wood has medium lustre and a mealy appearance, with conspicuous lines and arches on the radial surface and mottling on the tangential surface. The wood is classified as medium-weight to moderately heavy with a density of 530 to 720 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, flooring, carpentry, railway sleepers, boxes, crates, cooperage, sport articles, tool handles, canoes, and suitable for making plywood.

Syzygium micklethwaitii. Syzygium spp. Water berry, Water pear. Mzuari, Mzambarau, Mkongoro, Mlungiro (Sw).

The heartwood is greyish red, brown or pink; it is not clearly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, texture fine to medium. Growth rings are distinct. The wood is moderately heavy, with a density of 640 to 860 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, flooring, panelling, furniture, railway sleepers utensils, tool handles, plates, stools, carvings, vehicle bodies, interior trim, joinery, toys, boxes, crates, veneer, plywood, hardboard, particle board, bows and ribs of canoes, dugout canoes..

Vitex keniensis. Meru Oak. Mfuu (Sw)

The heartwood is pale grey-brown and indistinctly demarcated from the sapwood, with heartwood of older trees often dark stained and decorative. The grain is straight or wavy, texture coarse. The wood resembles teak, and often yellows after some time in service. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 430 to 570 kg/m³

Uses: The wood is used for furniture, coffin boards, paneling, veneer, tool handles, oxen yokes, light construction, flooring, joinery, interior trim, boatbuilding, toys, boxes, crates, carving, turnery, draining boards, hardboard, particle board and pulpwood.

Xeroderris stuhlmannii. Wing pod, Wing bean. Mnyinga, Mondogondo, Mumundu (Sw).

The heartwood is cream-coloured to dark yellow, occasionally with reddish streaks, and not distinctly demarcated from the sapwood. The grain is straight, rarely interlocked, texture moderately fine and even. The wood is heavy, with a density of 800 to 835 kg/m³

Uses: Furniture, railway sleepers, heavy construction, flooring, vehicle bodies, sporting goods, interior trim, joinery, poles and piles, carving, toys, turnery, veneer and plywood, boat building, handles, utensils, grain mortars.

Xymalos monospora. Lemonwood, Wild lemon

The heartwood is lemon-yellow to pale brown or greenish brown and not distinctly demarcated from the slightly paler sapwood. The grain is straight, texture fine and even. Quarter-sawn surfaces show an attractive silver-grain figure. The wood is medium-weight, with a density of 510 to 610 kg/m³

Uses: Light construction, posts, door frames, flooring, joinery, furniture, toys, boxes, crates, agricultural implements, utensils, handles, beehives, brush backs, carvings, turnery, veneer, plywood and pulp and paper products.

***Need Preservative Treatment when used in ground contact or for exterior applications*

Zanha Africana. Velvet-fruited zanha. Mkalya, Mkwanga (Sw).

The heartwood is pinkish to red-brown when freshly cut, turning pale brown to pinkish brown upon drying, and fairly distinctly demarcated from the yellowish white sapwood. Grain wavy to interlocked, texture fine. The wood is fairly heavy with a density of 705 to 900 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, door frames, tool handles, household implements and articles, flooring, boat building, vehicle bodies, furniture, toys, agricultural implements, railway sleepers and turnery.

Zanthoxylum gillettii. African satinwood, White African mahogany

The heartwood is pale yellow to bright yellow or yellowish brown, darkening upon exposure, and indistinctly demarcated from the narrow sapwood. The grain is interlocked, texture fine to moderately coarse. Quartercut surfaces show a stripe figure and backsawn surfaces occasionally have a fiddleback figure. The wood has a silky lustrate wood is moderately heavy to heavy, with a density of 720 to 1040 kg/m³

Uses: Construction, flooring, joinery, interior trim, panelling, doors, furniture, cabinet work, railway sleepers, handles, ladders, sporting goods, agricultural implements, drums, toys, boxes, crates, turnery, veneer and plywood.

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